

Hybrid Work Culture And Employee Productivity: An Empirical Analysis Of Key Influencing Factors In IT Organizations

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ABSTRACT

The change in work culture of IT organization after COVID-19 has redefined organizational work practices and employee productivity. After COVID-19 most of the IT organization adopted hybrid work culture. In hybrid work culture, IT organization allow employees to work from home for some days and work in office for remaining days. The study empirically examines that the employee productivity is influencing by various key factors in hybrid work culture. Key factors like work-life balance, working hours flexibility, technology infrastructure, support of leadership, communication, on side and off side work environment. Primary data collected from IT organization employees using structured questionnaire with five Likert scale as strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree. After analysing the data which was collected from IT employees the finding are the key factors like work-life balance, working hours flexibility, technology infrastructure, support of leadership, communication, on side and off side work environment significantly enhance employee productivity in hybrid work culture. The study provides actionable insights for IT organizations by using sustainable hybrid work environment policies.

Keywords: Hybrid Work Culture, Employee Productivity, Work Life Balance, Flexibility in Work, Leadership support, Communication, Technology Infrastructure.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has changed the organization working way, especially the drastic change occurred in the Information Technology organization. Traditional work from office work model replaced by remote working model. This change ensures business continuity with safeguarding employee health. As COVID-19 restrictions removed that is after post pandemic, many IT organization change their working culture from full remote work to hybrid work model. In hybrid work model employee work in the combination of work from home and onsite work environment. This change has redefined the organization work practice, employee role, leader role, communication, policies and productivity expectations.

Fig 1. Work from home VS Work from office

<https://co-offiz.com/will-work-from-home-wfh-eventually-pivot-into-co-working-near-home-cn/>
Hybrid work model provides flexibility to employees by allowing them to balance professional responsibilities and personal commitments. However, the effectiveness of this work model depends on various individual and organizational factors that influence employee productivity. Key factors such as flexible working hours, work life balance, robust technology infrastructure, effective communication,

leadership support and conducive work environment play important role in determining productivity outcomes in hybrid work environment. The growing adoption of hybrid work culture in IT sector, evidence examining how the above factors influence employee productivity.

Employee productivity is very important factor to determine organization performance and competitiveness in IT sector. In hybrid work model knowledge-based work, collaboration and innovation is matter for employee productivity. The hybrid work model has both opportunities and challenges. The organization require to redesign policies for employees, need to decide workflow and managerial practices for the employee productivity. The organization need to understand the key factors that enhance the productivity in a hybrid work model. For good productivity of employees, organization should develop effective strategies.

In this context, the present study has objective to examine which key factors influence employee productivity in hybrid mode within the IT sector. After analysing the primary data collected from employees working in IT organization through a structured questionnaire, this study seeks to provide evidence-based insights. This study can assist IT organizations to formulate sustainable hybrid work model policies. The findings are expected to contribute to the existing work model and offer practical implications for leaders and HR heads in the IT sector.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine the impact of work life balance and flexibility in work, on employee productivity in hybrid work model of IT organization.
2. To analyse the role of technology infrastructure and digital tools in facilitating effective communication and enhancing employee productivity for hybrid work model.
3. To assess the influence of leadership support and managerial practices on employee engagement and productivity within Hybrid work culture.
4. To evaluate the effect of the physical and remote work environment on employees' performance, motivation and overall productivity in Hybrid work model.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology follows the systematic way to achieve the objectives of the research study. It ensures the reliability and accuracy of findings. This analytical study focuses on to examine the key factors which influencing the employee productivity of IT organization employees who are currently working in Hybrid work model in Maharashtra.

1. **Research Design:** An analytical and descriptive research design was adopted to examine the employee perceptions of productivity related factors in hybrid work environment. The descriptive research is used to understand existing system and perceptions about the hybrid work culture in IT sector. The analytical method is used to interpret the data collection and find the relationship between dependent and independent variables.
2. **Population:** The data were collected from employees who are working in IT sector. Different communication platforms have used to collect the data. It includes participants across various employment levels and genders to ensure the sample was reasonable representation of the target population.
3. **Sample:** Using convenience sampling 107 responses was selected for data analysis. The sample size is 107 for the research study.
4. **Data Collection:** Primary data is used for research study data analysis. Structured questionnaire is used for data collection. Questionnaire designed with five Likert scale points as strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree.
5. **Data Analysis:** Data were analysed using descriptive method and using percentage analysis. Data visualization done using MS-Excel software. Tables and Graphs were used for data representation and interpretation of result.

Table 1: Key Factor wise responses received from IT organization employees

Sr. No.	Key Factor	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
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1	Work-life balance	44	39	13	5	1
2	Flexibility in working hours	44	35	17	4	1
3	Technology and Infrastructure	38	45	15	4	0
4	Communication	38	40	16	8	0
5	Leadership	38	37	22	5	0
6	Work Environment	38	42	17	5	0

Fig. 2: Key factor wise responses received from IT Organization employees

The questionnaire is based on six key factors are as follows:

Table 2: Key Factor wise questionnaire prepared for IT organization employees

Sr. No.	Key Factor	Question
1	Work-life balance	The hybrid work model allows me to maintain a healthy work-life balance, which enhances my productivity.
2	Flexibility in working hours	Having flexibility in work hours in a hybrid setup positively influences my performance.
3	Technology and Infrastructure	I have access to reliable technology and infrastructure that supports my productivity in a hybrid work environment.
4	Communication	Effective communication with my team and supervisors is maintained in the hybrid work model.
5	Leadership	Support and guidance from leadership positively impact my productivity while working in a hybrid setup.
6	Work Environment	My physical and digital work environment is conducive to staying focused and productive in a hybrid setting

Fig 3. Key Factors influencing Employee Productivity

The MS-Excel is used to draw horizontal bar chart. The data clearly indicates a strong positive perception

of hybrid work culture among employees with respect to productivity related key factors.

Interpretation of the data

- 1. Work life balance:** This factor shows the highest level of agreement, with 44% strongly agree and 39% agree responses. This indicates that hybrid work enhances productivity of employee by enabling better balance. This highlights that work-life balance is the important productivity factor.
- 2. Flexibility in work hours:** In this key factor, strongly agreed and agreed combined responses are 79%. This demonstrates the strong influence on employee productivity. This result suggests that autonomy over scheduling significantly improve employee performance in hybrid work system.
- 3. Technology and infrastructure:** For this key factor, 38% strongly agree and 45% agree responses received from IT employees. This indicates that access to reliable digital tools is largely sufficient and positively contributes to productivity.
- 4. Communication:** Communication effectiveness shows slightly lower agreement (78%) with comparatively higher neutral response (16%) and disagreement (8%). This shows that while communication is greatly effective, coordination challenges remain in hybrid work model.
- 5. Leadership:** In leadership section 38% strongly agree, 37% agree, 22% neutral responses received from employees. This implies that employee experience inconsistencies in leadership engagement and guidance across hybrid teams.
- 6. Work environment:** For work environment, 38% strongly agree, 42% agree responses received which reinforcing the importance of well-designed workspaces for both remote and on-site work model.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Based on the data analysis, the key findings are as follows:

- 1. Work life balance** is most influential factor in hybrid work environment. Employees are able to manage their personal and professional work in hybrid work model. Employees who experience reduced commuting time, flexible scheduling, ability to manage personal and professional responsibilities results higher job satisfaction and sustained work engagement. Work intensity and cognitive demands are high in IT organizations that improved work-life balance. It helps to reduce stress, burnout and it results in enhancing individual productivity and overall organizational performance.
 - 2. Flexible work hours** give freedom to employees to decide their working hours. It significantly improves the employee performance. Flexible work hours allow individuals to work during their peak productivity hours. The results says that autonomy over work schedules and fosters a sense of trust and accountability, it improved motivation and efficiency of employee. In hybrid work model, flexibility enables employees to manage their workload, family responsibilities, personal commitments that results in high quality output and timely completion of tasks.
 - 3. Proper use of technology and infrastructure** is very essential in hybrid model. Especially in IT organizations that rely heavily on digital platforms and real time collaborations. This study highlights that reliable internet connectivity, collaboration tools, secure system and appropriate hardware and software significantly influences employee's ability to perform tasks efficiently. Any defective technical infrastructure can disrupt workflow, increase delays in completion of work and that affects employee productivity.
 - 4. Communication effectiveness** requires for further improvement to reduce coordination gaps. In hybrid work model, sometimes employees experience coordination gaps due to reduction of face-to-face interactions, different time zone and dependency on digital communication tools. These coordination gaps can lead to misunderstandings between employees, delay in decision making and reduce the team work.
 - 5. Stronger leadership** support required in hybrid work model so that employees can work efficiently. Some team leaders demonstrate strong engagement and adaptability; others struggle for supervise and support remote teams. Inconsistent leadership may result in reduction of employee morale, unclear expectations and uneven employee performance. This finding emphasizes the need of leadership training, performance monitoring and employee engagement in hybrid work model.
- A conducive physical and digital work environment positively impacts focus and productivity.**
- 6.** Employees working from home or from office with well- integrated digital tools results in fewer distractions and improve the concentration. The hybrid work model allows employees to decide their

work environment which results in completion of work in time, creativity in their work and it increase the overall productivity of organization.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the findings, the following suggestions are proposed:

- 1. Creation of flexible work policies:** IT organization should create flexible work policies to systematically support work life balance. Clearly defined guidelines regarding working hours, availability expectations, performance metrics and hybrid attendance norms can reduce ambiguity. Formal policies also help employees to plan their work more effectively. It enhances trust between employees and management.
- 2. Investment in Digital Infrastructure and Cybersecurity:** To sustain productivity in hybrid work culture, organization must invest in advanced digital infrastructure which includes high speed connectivity, cloud-based platform and collaborative tools. Strengthening cybersecurity measures are equally important to protect organization data and maintain employee confidence in hybrid work system. Reliable and secure technology minimizes the operational cost and enables seamless collaboration across teams.
- 3. Leadership Development:** Leadership Development Program should design for team leaders. These programs should focus on virtual team engagement, outcome-based performance management and effective communion across physical and digital spaces. Strengthening managerial capabilities can enhance employee motivation, satisfaction, improve coordination and get the consistent good performance.
- 4. Clear communication Framework and collaborative tools:** Organization should create structured communication frameworks that defines communication channels, response timeline and meeting protocols. The effective use of collaboration tools such as project management software, video conferencing platforms can reduce miscommunication among hybrid employees. Clear communication framework enhances transparency, teamwork and coordination across department.
- 5. Adoption of regular feedback and monitoring mechanism:** Regular feedback system such as virtual check-ins, employee survey and performance review should be adopted to assess employee experiences and identify challenges in hybrid work model. Continuous feedback enables organizations to respond to employee concerns related to workload, well-being, technology and communication.
- 6. Optimization of physical and remote work environments:** Organization should optimize both physical office space and remote work setups to ensure consistent productivity across different work modes. Office environment should support collaboration, innovation while remote work setups should be supported through guidance, technology allowances and infrastructure support. Providing employees with optimize environment enhances focus and promotes sustained productivity in hybrid work culture.

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